

Fast tracking for the HL-LHC ATLAS detector

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ABSTRACT

During the High-Luminosity LHC, up to 200 simultaneous inelastic proton-proton collisions per bunch crossing are expected. This poses a significant challenge for the track reconstruction and its associated computing requirements due to the unprecedented number of particle hits in the tracker system. In order to tackle this challenge, dedicated algorithms have been developed to speed up the track reconstruction and further optimise the default algorithms of the ATLAS detector. The performance of this Fast Track Reconstruction is presented and compared to the one of the default Phase-II track reconstruction.

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1 Introduction

During the Run-2 the ATLAS experiment recorded data from up to $\langle\mu\rangle \approx 70$ proton-proton collisions per bunch-crossing (pile-up) as shown in Figure 1(a). For the HL-LHC era a pile-up regime between 140 and 200 is expected. In order to estimate the corresponding reconstruction time, a high- μ run was performed in 2017 using the Run-2 detector and software. As shown in Figure 1(b), the reconstruction time is increasing exponentially as a function of pile-up. This illustrates that the HL-LHC will become a challenge for tracking. However, it should be noted that the ATLAS detector was designed for a pile-up of $\langle\mu\rangle \lesssim 23$ and the software

Figure 1: Recorded Run-2 pile-up [1] (a) and CPU requirements for track reconstruction vs. η including high- μ run [2] (b).

was used unchanged for that high- μ run. This clearly shows that for the HL-LHC scenario work and R&D has to be performed in several areas: a new detector design that targets this challenging environment, but also an optimised reconstruction software that is based on the current track reconstruction software augmented or enhanced by new components as an outcome of dedicated R&D initiatives. These areas are presented in the following.

2 ATLAS Phase-II tracking

The current Inner Detector (ID) of the ATLAS experiment will due to radiation damage come to the end of its lifetime by the end of Run-3. Additionally, the ID operates at the current pile-up scenario at its bandwidth limit and the Transition Radiation Tracker (TRT) has up to 50% occupancy at $\langle\mu\rangle = 70$. In order to provide high tracking performance in the HL-LHC era, the ID will be replaced by an all-Silicon Inner Tracker (ITk)[3]. This new tracking detector was designed to provide a high tracking performance at up to $\langle\mu\rangle = 200$. As shown in Figure 2(a), it consists of five pixel layers which cover a pseudorapidity range of $|\eta| < 4$ and four strip layers which cover a range of $|\eta| < 2.7$. The ID for comparison covers a range of $|\eta| < 2.5$. The design of the ITk provides an approximate constant minimum number of hits over the full range of $|\eta| < 4$ as shown in Figure 2(b). Thus this design allows to obtain a high tracking performance over its full η range at $\langle\mu\rangle = 200$ while the bandwidth and the pixel surface is kept at a minimum.

Beside the replacement of the detector hardware, an adaption of the Run-2 tracking software to the ITk was performed. As the expected number of hits is increased, tighter track requirements, compared to Run-2, can be applied[4]. The applied track selection cuts result in a high and stable tracking efficiency over the full covered range as shown in Figure 3(a). Since the requirements for the number of hits per track were increased compared to Run-2, the fake rate can be decreased as shown in Figure 3(b). These simulations demonstrate the potential in tracking performance of the ITk for the HL-LHC era.

Figure 2: R-z view of the ITk (a) and the obtained number of hits per η (b) [5].

Figure 3: Comparison between the ID at $\langle\mu\rangle = 20$ and the ITk at $\langle\mu\rangle = 200$ [6]. The left plot shows the tracking efficiency versus $|\eta|$, the right plot show the fake rate versus $|\eta|$.

2.1 Computing requirements

The ITk simulations are currently performed using the Run-2 software. Thereby the biggest contributions to the event processing time are given by the (Silicon) Track Finding and the Ambiguity Resolution as shown in Table 1. Furthermore a major contribution to the ID is given by the TRT and Back Tracking. The tuning of the track reconstruction setup is always done with the aim to achieve a maximum physics

Table 1: CPU requirements for the individual stages of track reconstruction using the Run-2 software as presented in Reference [3]. The tabular shows a comparison between the contributions of the ITk at $\langle\mu\rangle = 200$ and the ID at $\langle\mu\rangle = 20$ as well as the total amount. The numbers are given in units of HS06s.

Detector	$\langle\mu\rangle$	Cluster Finding	Space Points	Si Track Finding	Ambiguity Resolution	TRT+Back Tracking	Primary Vertex	Total ITk/ID
ITk Layout	200	22	6.5	78	97	-	6	219
Run-2	20	1.5	0.7	23	15	19	0.5	64

performance within the available computing budget. Nonetheless the overview of CPU requirements, shown in Figure 4(a), predicts that the ITk with the Run-2 software using cuts adapted for the HL-LHC conditions achieves a better CPU performance at $\langle\mu\rangle = 200$ than the ID during Run-2 at $\langle\mu\rangle = 60$. The achieved improvement is a combination of the design of the new tracking detector together with an adequate adaption

of the track reconstruction software.

These improvements in the Inner Tracking system have been used to extrapolate the full ATLAS event reconstruction time to the HL-LHC environment, see Figure 4(b). Within the scenario using the current computing performance (blue circles) the track reconstruction requires $\approx 45\%$ of the CPU resources. Furthermore this extrapolation is still far above the assumed available resources, shown as black solid lines. In

Figure 4: Left: CPU requirements for track reconstruction with the ID during Run-2 and the simulated ITK as a function of the mean pile-up $\langle \mu \rangle$. The contributions of the Track Finding and the Ambiguity Resolution to the total reconstruction are shown separately [5]. Right: Extrapolation of ATLAS CPU requirements as a function of time. The blue circles labelled as Baseline show the estimates with the currently unchanged track reconstruction, while Conservative and Aggressive R&D scenarios lead to the improvements shown as blue triangles. The solid black lines show the assumed available CPU resources [2].

order to speed up the track reconstruction two different approaches can be performed. The first one is a speed up of the existing track reconstruction code, the second one is the R&D of new approaches. The first topic will be discussed in the following section. An overview of the second topic is presented in Section 4.

3 Fast track reconstruction

The fast track reconstruction[7], originally motivated by the question of whether a high level software trigger would be possible for HL-LHC conditions, was a dedicated study to determine how the current ATLAS track reconstruction workflow can be modified and tuned in order to achieve the desired HL-LHC event throughput. The study was performed using the ITk detector geometry at a pile-up of 140 and 200. The goal of the study was to decrease the CPU requirements for track reconstruction as far as possible while the loss in physics performance should be kept to a minimum. The unmodified workflow, as shown in Figure 5, was then successively changed with the primary goal to minimise the event processing time. In this first assessment, slight degradation of physics performance was accepted in order to allow an aggressive estimation of achievable speed up factors. The performed modifications will be described in the following.

As a first step the Ambiguity Resolution, since it is the main contributor as seen in Table 1, will be

Figure 5: Track reconstruction workflow for the ITk geometry with all components involved.

disabled. Since this part performs due to historical reasons additional tasks, a precise track fit would be missing. Furthermore the b-tagging efficiency is assumed to be reduced due to the missing NN cluster splitting in jets. Some of the workload is thereby moved to the combinatorial track finding stage instead, in order to suppress the creation of ambiguities in the first place. In addition the combinatorial track finder performed in this workflow the task to estimate the final track parameters. Therefore the tracking cuts in the track finder were tightened as shown in Table 2. As the cuts become more strict a speed up effect is

Table 2: Applied tracking cuts in the track finder of the fast track reconstruction[7]. The default values are given in brackets. Here z_0 , the longitudinal impact parameter, is defined with respect to the mean position of the beam spot.

Requirement	Pseudorapidity interval		
	$ \eta < 2.0$	$2.0 < \eta < 2.6$	$2.6 < \eta < 4.0$
Pixel+Strip hits	≥ 9 (7)	≥ 8 (7)	≥ 7 (7)
unique hits	≥ 7 (1)	≥ 6 (1)	≥ 5 (1)
shared hits	≤ 2 (no cut)	≤ 2 (no cut)	≤ 2 (no cut)
p_T [MeV]	> 1000 (900)	> 400 (400)	> 400 (400)
$ z_0 $ [cm]	≤ 15 (20)	≤ 15 (20)	≤ 15 (20)

expected as well. Additionally an approximated material model and cluster correction was applied, while the full detailed cluster calibration remained unchanged for the fast track reconstruction chain.

The next modification considers the seeding. While during Run-2 approximately 20% of CPU time was spent in the seeding it is assumed to be increased up to 50% at HL-LHC pile-up. As the ITk will consist of five pixel layers and these cover the full range of $|\eta| < 4$, the pixel detector contributes the major amount of seeds, as shown in Figure 6. Therefore the goal of the study was to improve the purity of pixel seeds

Figure 6: Mean number of accepted seeds in the ITk pixel and strip detector versus $|\eta|$ [3].

while the seed finding in the strip detector is dropped entirely. The increased purity is thereby assumed to speed up the CPU times spent in road build and track finding, too. Additionally the recovery strategy for Bremsstrahlung[7] was also temporarily disabled in the track finding.

For the data pre-processing stage, code optimisations of the pixel detector and the strip clustering were performed. Since the strip space point formation is very CPU consuming and is only required for strip seeding, it was entirely removed from the workflow. The last aspect covers the RD53B front-end chip[8] of the ITk pixel detector. Its design allows to read out multiple pixels simultaneously in a tree-like way and therewith to read out pixel clusters. The underlying bit-coding achieves a significant data compression such that an event in the pixel detector is of comparable size to the strip detector. However there is no decoding software available yet. Therefore within this study the Run-2 raw data decoding was used and the event sizes scaled to ITk event sizes. For Monte Carlo events the decoding of simulated hits from ROOT[9] files was used.

3.1 Physics performance

In this section the physics performance achieved with the fast track reconstruction for particles with $p_T > 1$ GeV using the full range of the ITk is presented, starting with the reconstruction efficiency as shown in Figure 7. A slight degradation of the efficiency is observable for all pseudorapidity bins with more significant reductions in the ITk barrel-endcap transition region at $|\eta| \approx 1.5$ and at the very forward region. The dependency on the transverse momentum also shows a slight decrease in most bins with a more significant deviation in low- p_T regions. As the multiple scattering becomes a more dominant effect in low- p_T regions, this observation is an expected effect of the material model approximations. As a consequence of the

Figure 7: Track reconstruction efficiency for single μ with a p_T of 2 GeV (a) and 100 GeV (b) versus η . The dependency of the efficiency on p_T is shown for $t\bar{t}$ events with $\langle\mu\rangle = 200$ (c) [7].

reduced efficiencies, this results in a lower number of reconstructed tracks, see Figure 8(a). On the other hand the similar amount of reconstructed tracks indicates no significantly increased fake-rate. Moreover the reconstructed tracks have an almost identical amount of hits in the pixel and strip detector as shown in Figure 8(b) and (c) respectively.

The track parameter resolutions are shown in Figure 9 for single μ . Most of these distributions are in good agreement with the default reconstruction. Noteworthy is within this set the more significant loss of $\approx 20\%$ in the p_T resolution of 2 GeV single μ which is again an effect of the applied material model approximations. Furthermore a loss of $\approx 50\%$ in z_0 resolution is observed for 100 GeV single μ in the $|\eta|$ region around 2. This is a consequence of the applied cluster correction. The key message that can be derived from this set is that the sources are well understood and therefore can be improved in the future.

Since the initial motivation of the study was to reduce the CPU consumption, the achieved performance is shown in Figure 10. It is observable that an outstanding improvement was achieved. Compared to the default ITk track reconstruction a speed up of a factor 6-7 was achieved for 140 and 200 pile-up. Comparing the fast track reconstruction at $\langle\mu\rangle = 200$ to the Run-2 reconstruction at $\langle\mu\rangle = 60$ it becomes even around a factor 8 in speed up. Though this was still based on the Run-2 software without including any benefits of the

Figure 8: Mean number of reconstructed track (a), associated hits in the pixel (b) and strip detector (c) versus η [7].

Acts project[10]. However the therewith achieved performance promises a significant reduction in ATLAS computing requirements in the HL-LHC era covering the data processing and Monte Carlo reconstructions. Also heavy ion physics would benefit from these results, as high centrality heavy ion collisions impose a similar high multiplicity environment. A consequence of the reduction is then that the CPU resources spent in event generation and Geant4[11, 12] simulations will become the dominant part while tracking will be only a minor contributor.

4 Further R&D projects

The last section showed that the tracking can become sufficiently fast for HL-LHC conditions in the ATLAS experiment. It was also presented in Figure 7 and 9 that the achieved physics performance was reduced compared to the default reconstruction. In order to improve the physics performance, further R&D is required: one candidate here is the inclusion of software from the Acts project. This project is an open-source collection of tracking tools and algorithms from contributors of various collaborations. It provides a modular software design that provides easy accessible interfaces for R&D. It is crucial to improve all kinds of reconstruction (e.g. e/γ , μ , b -tagging,...) in the future.

Beyond this project there are further perspectives e.g. from machine learning. For that purpose the TrackML challenge[13], a public accessible track reconstruction competition, was held. Also efforts into adapting tracking to new hardware architectures like FPGAs or GPUs are items of investigation. All over many different ideas and inspirations are currently in the process of making in order to achieve the best possible performance for the HL-LHC conditions.

Figure 9: Resolution of d_0 , z_0 (the transverse and longitudinal impact parameters) and the relative p_T for single μ with 2 and 100 GeV versus η [7].

5 Conclusions

The expected pile-up provided by the HL-LHC will become a challenge for track reconstruction. In order to handle the increasing complexity, ATLAS will install the new tracking detector ITk which is designed for that purpose. For the track reconstruction software adaptations of the software used for Run-2 were performed which provided a significant improvement in CPU resource requirements but which is still above the expected available CPU resources. A fast track reconstruction was investigated for CPU requirement reduction by modifying and adapting the track reconstruction workflow. Thereby a speed up of a factor 8 between the ITk at $\langle\mu\rangle = 200$ and the Run-2 detector at $\langle\mu\rangle = 60$ was achieved. Since the study was focused on optimisation of the CPU performance a reduced physics performance was observed. In order to conserve a high physics performance standard in the context of fast track reconstruction the software project Acts will be involved in the future. This project provides by its structure an ideal ground for tracking R&D and is therefore expected

Figure 10: Reconstruction time for Run-2, default and fast ITk track reconstruction [7].

to become beneficial to all reconstructions. Beside the development in Acts, ATLAS is also actively investing into R&D to test new ideas and technologies concerning track reconstruction performance.

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